

Design and Development of a Secure Mobile Money Integration for E-Commerce Platforms: A Software Engineering Approach

By

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Declaration

I declare that this report and the accompanying artefact and annexes as results of my original work undertaken by myself without support of anyone and that this work was been done in strict conformance with Staffordshire University's policies, guidelines and regulations.

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Abstract

This report presents the development of a secure Android application designed to integrate mobile money payments into e-commerce platforms, aiming to enhance user trust in online transactions. The project followed a structured approach, incorporating object-oriented design and agile methodologies to ensure robust development and security. User requirements were gathered through semi-structured interviews, guiding the system analysis and design, which included the use of diagrams such as use case, sequence, conceptual models, and class diagrams. The application leverages Firebase NoSQL for data management and implements Façade and Chain of Responsibility design patterns to secure transaction processes. The results demonstrate that the application effectively addresses the security concerns associated with mobile payments, thus contributing to increased consumer confidence in e-commerce.

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List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
ADMMC	Agile based development methodology for mobile commerce
AMDD	Agile Model Driven Development
APK	Android Package File
CIA	Confidentiality Integrity Availability
DevOps	Development and Operations
FDD	Features Driven development
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
ICT	Information Communication Technology
JDK	Java Development Kit
JRE	Java Runtime Environment
MBPS	Mega-Bytes per second
Mpesa	Mobile Money
NoSQL	No only Sequence Query Language
OODP	Object Oriented Design and Programming
OOP	Object Oriented Programming
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDLC	System Development Life Cycle
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SMEs	Small and Medium Size Enterprises
SQL	Sequence Query Language
SSD	Solid State Drive
TDD	Test Driven Development
UML	Unified Modelling Language
XP	Extreme Programming

CHAPTER ONE

PROJECT INTRODUCTION AND SYNOPSIS

1.1 Introduction

According to Bhan (2014), less than 30% of Africans have bank accounts and a significantly smaller number of them have credit cards. In contrast, the number of people with mobile money account exceeds that of those with bank accounts in at least nine African countries; Kenya included (Bhan, 2014). Ekekwe (2015) lists fraud as one of the reasons why Africa is lagging in ecommerce when compared to other continents. He however notes that, the major reason behind this is not only because of a predominantly high level of fraud, but due to people's perceptions that online transactions are susceptible to fraud. This perception makes them paranoid and sceptical about giving their bank and credit card credentials online.

In defiance of this, a white paper published by one of the largest online retailer in Kenya (Jumia.co.ke), ranks Kenya as the 21st most connected country in the world, with 58% of the population having internet access (Zab, 2015). These statistics further manifests that, 99.9% of internet users access internet using smart phones and furthermore that, android smart phones dominate the market at 92.2% (Zab, 2015). Since the dominant hindrance of the adoption of ecommerce in Kenya is the mode of payment; it is presumed that, integrating mobile money payment in ecommerce platforms would help alleviate distrust (Ekekwe, 2015).

Binsaleh & Hassan (2011) reviews the most influential software engineering approaches employed when developing mobile applications. Their work, which is based on earlier findings of Ngai and Gunasekaran (2007), identifies mobile ecommerce development as an emerging area of research with very low resources available when compared to research on web-based ecommerce systems. Although their research work only focused on the requirements gathering - with suggestions of development methodologies, it also proposes for the application and evaluation of these methodologies.

In this project, an approach similar to that employed by Ngai and Gunasekaran (2007) is adopted but instead of focussing only on requirements gathering, the project extends to mobile application development while considering new developments in the area in recent

years. It is hypothetically anticipated that, by following well engineered software development approaches, it is possible to develop a high-quality application that addresses the distrust problem highlighted by Ekekwe (2015).

1.2 Background Information

Developing countries present unlimited investments opportunities in technology because they tend to lag most of the time in adopting modern technologies, but Kenya, a country in the eastern side of the Africa continent with an estimated population of about 50 million people, was an exception to this rule on issue mobile money. Motivated by the technologies dominant in the automation era, the idea of having a paperless economy dawned to her population sooner than later - leading to a paradigm shift in the country's financial sector.

Currently, Kenya has five mobile service providers namely; Safaricom, Airtel, Telkom, Equitel and Sema mobile. Safaricom commands the largest market share with a customer base of about 71.2%, while its closest competitor; Airtel, ranks at a distance second with about 17.6% customer base (Twinpine Network, 2016). Based on these statistics, the Mpesa mobile payment service offered by Safaricom commands a large market and has over time surpassed the market enjoyed by the Kenyan banks and microfinance institutions (Central Bank of Kenya, 2016). For instance, the microfinance institution with the largest customer base has 540,648 accounts compared to Safaricom's 25 million Mpesa accounts that transact a daily average of approximately \$150 million (Central Bank of Kenya, 2016).

The significant size of this market by customer base and transaction value presents vast opportunities to businesses. Additionally, this market is supported by a large penetration of internet services in the country and wide adoption of smart phones (Zab, 2015). Despite these glaring investment opportunities, very little effort has been done to integrate mobile money with ecommerce platforms and where this has been done, the solutions are proprietary and complicated to adopt. Safaricom provides Application Programming Interface (API) to enhance such integration but this requires extensive expertise to implement. These and several other dynamics have led to a lack of off-the-shelf solutions that can be used by SME's with limited expertise and resources.

This project takes advantage of advancements in mobile computing technology by focusing on the android operating system and android applications development integration with

mobile payment. The application uses Mpesa; a popular payment option in Kenya. Mpesa stands for mobile money with M representing mobile and “pesa” being the Swahili language name for money. Mpesa is a trademark of Safaricom Limited and is franchised to independent agents who are distributed across the country and who earn a commission when people withdraw money using their pre-allocated agency numbers. These agents’ additionally help in the registration of new customers to the service and in depositing money into Mpesa accounts. Safaricom has fixed charges for withdrawals and transfers between customers but does not charge any fees on deposit in Mpesa account. Mpesa platform offers a variety of services such as bill payments, buying of goods and services, and sending of money between Mpesa account holders. Businesses that want to use the pay bill or the buy goods and services option must register with Safaricom to obtain a pay bill number or a till number respectively.

The application presented in chapter four of this report is integrated with Mpesa API to accommodate the buy goods options for mobile commerce payments. This option is preferred because it is a widely used payment option by small businesses (Twinpine Network, 2016). Additionally, the application is designed to allow completion of transaction only when the buyer can verify their payment using a receipt that is automatically sent to them by Safaricom after payment. This verification is important because, Safaricom’s Mpesa polices requires both the buyer and the seller to receive transaction messages for a transactions to be deemed complete and successful.

1.3 Aim of the project

The main aim of the project is to develop an ecommerce android application with integrated mobile money payment system while following well engineered software development and testing approaches, to address the security issues associated with other forms of online payments.

1.4 Objectives of the project

- a) To critically investigate software engineering approaches in the development of a secure android application.
- b) To critically investigate the methodologies used in testing secure android applications.
- c) To develop a secure android application for mobile payments.

- d) To critically evaluate the effectiveness of the developed android application in addressing the security issues associated with ecommerce payments.

1.5 Resources used in the project

A. Hardware

- Laptop – Windows 8 with Intel Core i5 Processor, 1.6 GHz, 500 HDD
- Personal Computer – Windows 10 with Intel Core 2 Duo Processor, 1.6 GHz, 500 HDD (backup)
- Android Mobile Phone (Samsung Grand 2) – API 19 Version 4.4.2 KitKat or above).
- Nokia 5 API 26, Version 8.0.0 (Oreo)
- Internet connection of 30MBPS.
- Safaricom Subscriber Identification Module (SIM) Card.

B. Software

- Android Studio and SDK Tools for creation, debugging, testing of codes and the application.
- Java runtime environment (JRE).
- Mobile and Tab Android emulation software integrated in Android studio.
- Bluestacks for Android emulation on windows.
- Microsoft Office 365 Applications (Word, Excel, PowerPoint)
- Microsoft Visio for designing UML diagrams.
- Databases (SQLite, MYSQL and Firebase NoSQL).
- Shared hosting, PHP 5.0.
- Firebase or Google App Engine platform for data Synchronisation.

C. Reading/ reference resources

- Staffordshire online library
- Google books and Google Scholar.
- Electronic journals, publications, articles and reports.
- Books

1.6 Project deliverables

- Literature review on software engineering approaches presented as section one in chapter two of the report.

- Literature review on the development and testing of secure android applications presented as section two in chapter two of the report.
- System analysis and design diagrams of the proposed android application presented in the first section of chapter four of the report.
- A secure android application for mobile payments appended to this report and presented, analysed and evaluated in chapter four and five of this report.
- Test plan and test reports showing how various aspect of software engineering were implemented, tested and evaluated.

1.7 Scope of the project

To achieve project objectives, the project follows three important approaches critically discussed by Pressman (2010) and by Blaude & Bernstein (2010) in their books on software engineering. These approaches are complemented with the current developments in this area.

Issues relating to trust and security from a social science perspective do not form the basis of this project. The scope of the project is limited to; investigation and application of software engineering approaches employed in the development of secure android applications, the databases used in such applications, best practices and software testing and evaluation strategies among other complementary areas of computer science.

1.8 Significance of the project

Integrating a mobile payment system with a mobile ecommerce platform will help in promoting customers trust on online payments in the following ways.

- a) The project provides traders with a mobile commerce application that has a trusted payment option. This option will take care of the customers who abstain from online transactions because they do not trust bank, credit and debit cards as modes of online payments.
- b) The application will also help businesses in increasing online sales to customers who have limited or no access to personal computers.
- c) The project creates an alternative online payment mechanism that is not directly connected to bank, credit or debit cards.

1.9 Chapter and Project Summary

In this chapter, the problem that motivated the project and its solutions are presented. A basic synopsis of the project that includes the background and the aim of project; supported by the specific objectives of the project are also highlighted. These are followed by the project requirements in terms of hardware, software, reading resources and finally the deliverables from project. The last part of this section outlines the scope of the project and the significance of undertaking the project. The rest of the report is organised as follows:

Chapter two, follows next, with literature review on software engineering approaches and on the development and testing of a reasonably secure android application for mobile payments. This review is supplemented with additional literature that is deemed to contribute towards the achievement of the project objectives. A detailed methodology employed in the project is given in chapter three while in chapter four, the android application is presented, discussed and the development processes analysed. The report ends in chapter five where the whole project is evaluated against its objectives. The main conclusions are also made in this chapter and some areas recommendations for further research.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

In the accompanying sections of this chapter, literature on software engineering approaches employed when developing software applications and the methodologies used for testing secure mobile applications is reviewed. The chapter begins with software engineering definitions that are then followed by a review that is classified based on the objectives of the project. In this respect, software engineering approaches from the perspective of software development methodologies and that of software development paradigms are reviewed. Later on, literature review on development and testing of secure mobile applications - with an emphasis on android applications development is undertaken.

2.2. Software Engineering Approaches

Braude and Bernstein (2010) describes software engineering as a process that comprises of development, testing and maintenance of software. Shull, Singer & Sjøberg (2008) additionally view software engineering as a people-oriented process. Furthermore, Robal *at al.*, (2015) define software engineering as: *“the application of a systematic, disciplined, quantifiable approach to the development, operation and maintenance of software; that is, the application of engineering to software.”*

The definitions above at least touches on one or more of the 4Ps in software development; that is, people, process, project and product (Blaude & Bernstein, 2010). To ensure a seamless process where all the above Ps are well coordinated when developing software, many scholars have come up with several software development methodologies that highlight all the aspects of software development as favoured by different types of software projects.

Most of these methodologies are modifications of the original System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) through: re-arrangement of its phases, addition of complementary activities or a total overhaul (Pressman, 2010). Blaude and Bernstein (2010) classify these methods as either modern or traditional. They discuss the agile methodology as a modern approach and waterfall methodology as a traditional one.

While a software development methodology defines the steps or the model to follow while undertaking project activities and its related processes, software development paradigms involve following concepts, patterns and theories while implementing different phases of the preferred methodology (Allardice, 2013).

2.2.1 Traditional software development approaches

Traditionally, software development followed a sequence defined by various models that existed back then. The main traditional models highlighted by Pressman (2010) include: the waterfall model, incremental process model, evolutionary process model, spiral model and concurrent model.

The original waterfall model was the first methodology introduced for software development (Pressman, 2010). The model has six phases and each phase must be completed before moving to the next phase as illustrated below.

Figure 2.1: The original waterfall model

Waterfall model (Blaude & Bernstein, 2010)

Opponents of the waterfall model argue that it led to a chaotic software development process that focused on the order of software development as opposed to the product (Pressman, 2010). Pressman (2010) highlights how these issues are addressed by the incremental model which mainly focuses on the production of incremental functionalities upon which developers can build on after input from stakeholders. But incremental model has not evaded criticism as well, it has been criticised because it overlooks the need for prototyping which is sometimes a key milestone in the software development (Blaude & Bernstein, 2010). The evolutionary model is seen by some as the solution to the prototyping challenges overlooked in the

incremental model as it requires the presentation of a prototype upon which developers can iteratively build on, based on the user's feedback (Pressman, 2010). On the other hand, the spiral model, another model in this category, is a composite of most of the features of other models but which calls for evolutionary releases of the initial prototype and is argued to be one of the major developments in this category (Pressman, 2010).

Although most of the above software development methodologies are not very popular today, it is not surprising to find some organizations and developers who still use them in their software development (Fonseca & Vieira, 2013). Their continued use is not mainly contingent on their significance but on factors such as experience of the developers, resistance to change, size of the project, and in cases where the project risk is low (Ambler, 2017).

2.2.2 Agile methodology

Agile software development methodology is the most popular and widely practiced modern software engineering approach today (Braude & Bernstein, 2010). It has become popular over time because it emphasizes on the importance of teams who have control over their work. The methodology also emphasises the importance of communication and collaboration in software development; a factor whose oversight has been argued to have contributed to mass failure of software projects in the past (The Standish Group, 2014).

To add to the merits of the agile methodology, Pressman (2010) sees it as a tool for managing changes in user requirements even late in the project. He also argues that, while late changes are viewed as additional work in other methodologies, in agile methodology, they are seen as opportunities. Although the methodology comprises of iterative processes, it has been seen to help in efficient production of software that quite often than not, meet and exceeded customer's expectations (Braude & Bernstein, 2010).

Figure 2.2: Graphical representation of the agile methodology

Source: (Mueller & Wickett, 2016)

Most agile processes are characterized by incremental and iterative software development cycles, with the major differentiation in these processes being the practices and tactics used during the software development process (Pressman, 2010). Some of the most popular agile processes are Scrum, Kanban, Extreme programming (XP), Feature Driven Development (FDD), DevOps and Test Driven Development (TDD).

2.2.2.1 Extreme Programming (XP)

Braude & Bernstein (2010) explains XP as an agile process that follows many short development cycles agreed upon by team members who have flexible testing times. Pressman (2010) additionally argues that, in XP, listening is an activity that must be taken seriously while quality and customer satisfaction are the ultimate achievements. The methodology emphasizes on quality rather than delivery on time, and software is developed using small releases that are tested within agreed timing. In agile XP, passionate developers look at the development process as a game which is won by satisfying customer needs (Pressman, 2010).

Figure 2.3: Illustration of Extreme programming (XP) methodology

Extreme Programming (XP) at a Glance

Source: (Meier, 2014)

2.2.2.2 Agile Scrum Methodology

Schwaber (2004) in his book on software development using agile scrum methodology, views scrum methodology as a process that empowers development teams and that is highly focused on satisfying customer requirements.

As shown in the figure below, in contrast to the waterfall model where software would be completed and then evaluated, scrum advocates for lean teams who develop and test small software units which are regularly integrated towards the complete system; the process also advocates for fixed-length iterations referred to as sprints.

Figure 2.4: An illustration of the Agile Scrum Methodology

Source: (Scrum, 2018)

Almeida (2017) looks at the agile scrum framework as an improvement of the spiral model where spirals which used to take too long to complete in the spiral model, are modified to sprints and completion period reduced to two weeks, and in some cases one month.

Pair programming is a popular practice in scrum methodology where two programmers work together, one writing the system code while the other looks for mistakes. Schwaber (2004) recommends a team of upto nine while using a scrum framework in software project management.

Almeida (2017) finds out several bottlenecks in the scrum methodology majorly related to organisational culture and resistant to change that affects the scrum methodology in modern development enviroment. However, several reviews of the methodology shows that, the

merits of this methodology, quite often than not, exceeds its demerits (Blaude & Bernstein, 2014; Pressman, 2010).

2.2.2.3 Features Driven Development (FDD)

FDD advocates for development of software through incremental features or functionalities (Ambler, 2005). The process involves defining the overall model first and then a features list upon which the plan, design and software development are based on. The features list forms the milestones to be used when reviewing the progress of the project. This approach takes all the principles of agile methodology as listed in the agile manifesto and follows an iterative process where independent features are tested and presented to the customer for feedback and then updated again to take the customer’s feedback into account (Ambler, 2005).

Figure 2.5: Features Driven development model

Source: (Ambler, 2005)

2.2.2.4 Development and Operations (DevOps)

DevOps software development methodology advocates for continuous integration of software development, operations and quality assurance (Bhens, Lau, & Markovitch, 2015). This methodology is quite comprehensive and requires the involvement of the software development team and specialists from other ICT areas in the software development projects. This methodology thrives in a culture that allows for experimentation and continuous practice (Mueller & Wickett, 2016).

Figure 2.6: Illustration of Agile DevOps Methodology

Source: (Mueller & Wickett, 2016)

2.2.3 Object Oriented, Analysis and Design

Allardice (2013) explains the importance of using an object oriented approach in software development while using java and other object oriented programming languages. Additionally, while referring to the classical waterfall model, he notices that, object orientation in software development is mostly employed in the system analysis and design, and in programming phases of the project. In system analysis and design, the Unified Modelling Language (UML) is used.

Figure 2.7: Sample Object Oriented Analysis and Design diagrams designed using UML

2.2.3.1 Principles of object-oriented programming

The four principles of OOP are: abstraction, polymorphism, encapsulation and inheritance. Abstraction is used to simplify the functionality of various objects that makes up an application to reduce the complexity of the application by hiding unnecessary details from the user. Encapsulation is used to hide objects; where details of functionalities of a class; that is, data and the code, are wrapped up in one object to hide them from other objects.

Polymorphism means that an object can take many forms while Inheritance means that, some classes in the application inherit functionalities and/or methods from others (Allardice, 2013).

Although inheritance reduces complexity and encourages code re-use, it can as well cause problems. For instance, while using this principle, objects embrace “is a” relationship which can lead to the creation of multiple unnecessary objects. Lagorio, Servetto & Zucca (2012) recommends composition over inheritance to avoid this problem.

In figure 4.8 below, the item data source class on the left side has five activities encapsulated as one object. It represents composition; on the other hand, the five activities are represented as five objects or interfaces to represent inheritance.

Figure 2.8: Illustration of OOP principles

2.2.3.2 Design patterns: Elements of Re-usable Object Oriented Software

Gamma *et al*, (1997) came up with twenty three design patterns for solving known software problems. They described their main use as to enhance code re-use, maintainability and to speed up software development process.

Table 2.0: Classification of design patterns by Purpose and by Scope

By Purpose				
		Creational	Structural	Behavioral
By Scope	Class	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Factory Method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapter (class) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interpreter Template Method
	Object	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Abstract Factory Builder Prototype Singleton 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapter (object) Bridge Composite Decorator Façade Flyweight Proxy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chain of Responsibility Command Iterator Mediator Memento Observer State Strategy Visitor

Although design patterns are not exactly OOP principles, they extend OOP. They solve the redundancy problems like the one illustrated in Figure 4.8 in the previous section which illustrated that; calling methods implemented using composition is more practical than those implemented using inheritance because composition requires a single instantiation and inheritance requiring multiple instantiations (Allardice, 2013).

2.3 Development and Testing of secure mobile applications

The software engineering methodologies and paradigms employed when developing and testing mobile applications are not so different from those applied when developing any other software. However, there a number of factors specific to mobile applications that requires additional considerations. Wasserman (2010) in his survey on issues in mobile application development highlights security and testing as two of the major issues that need particular consideration. He sees this to be largely contributed by the ability to install new applications on mobile phones; which have the capability to interact with other applications. He also highlights the complexity of testing mobile applications due to their unlimited versions and devices.

2.3.1 Methodologies for Developing secure mobile applications

Hameed & Oudah (2013) in their quest to improve agile methodology for use in the development of ecommerce mobile applications - rule out the use of traditional models in

mobile applications development - and emphasizes on how the agile methodology is a good fit for this purpose. They empirically study a model that combines extreme programming (XP) practices supplemented with Scrum management structure and refer it to Agile based development methodology for mobile commerce (ADMMC). The model highly borrows from the research of Binsaleh & Hassan (2011) and that of Amber (2007); Agile Model Driven Development (AMDD), which were proposed for general purpose software development.

ADMMC as explained by Hameed & Oudah (2013) takes into account majority of the complexities involved when developing mobile applications. While testing the ADMMC model, Hameed & Oudah (2013) compares the five phases of the model namely; exploration, release planning, iterations to release, productionization and maintenance to those in the traditional waterfall model, and concludes by supporting the model's applicability in developing an ecommerce mobile application. They also note that it adds unlimited benefits to the development process when compared to the waterfall model.

Scrum methodology, which is a key agile methodology, has also not been overlooked. Kaleel & Harishankar (2013) applied scrum when developing a secure incremental back up application. Scrum as explained by Schwaber (2004) uses sprints which Kaleel & Harishankar (2013) refer to as low level SDLC processes of the waterfall model.

In their methodology, they give the four agile-scrum phases of the model as requirements gathering, planning, sprint and reviews, and release. These sprints are allocated to teams who have short daily progress update meetings. Kaleel & Harishankar (2013) recommends scrum when developing software in a rapidly changing environment as is the case in mobile development.

2.3.2 Security Requirements in mobile applications

To ensure that security is integrated in every phase of the software development, Paul (2014) gives a set of software security requirements and classifies them as either core, general, operational or other.

Figure 2.9: Software Security Requirements

Software security requirements, Source: (Paul, 2014)

Conrad, Misener and Feldman (2016) and Paul (2014) unanimously propose Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability (CIA triad) as the basic foundation of all forms of security whether physical, digital or software security. .

2.3.3 Security Design and Implementation

When designing various functionalities of the software, features that promote the confidentiality, integrity and availability of the data it stores, processes, and sends, must also be designed. Paul (2014) indicates that: confidentiality can be enhanced through cryptographic and masking techniques, integrity through hashing and referential integrity; and availability through an easy to use interface that allows navigation, regular synching and automated back up through replication. Additional requirements such as authentication, authorization and accountability should also be considered to protect the system and its data against unauthorized access (Paul, 2012).

Security planning is important because it ensures that security is built-in and not bolted-in software (Pressman, 2010). Core software security must be integrating in software during development and the general, operational and other requirements controlled during software use through polices and user training (Paul, 2012). After planning on the security measures, a cost-benefit analysis of the investment is done to evaluate the viability of various security implementations (Conrad, Misener and Feldman, 2016). This is done hand in hand with the internal and external requirements such as adaptability to change and collaborative development.

2.3.4 Software testing methodologies

Software testing methodologies are better explained in two respects; 1) using a test driven development approach and 2) using software testing strategies. The former is explained in a consequent section as test driven development while the latter is discussed in line with white and black box software testing strategies and various types of testing; such as unit, integrated, regression, functional and acceptance testing (Pressman, 2010).

2.3.4.1 Software testing strategies

Everett & McLeod (2007) comprehensively lists the basic types of testing strategies as static, white box, black box and performance testing. They explain on how to write a test plan and test cases that imitate the business environment.

White box testing is a practice adopted by developers and other project team members who understand the programming language in use and the holistic design of the system or the unit they are testing (Pressman, 2010). The test involves looking into the structure of the software including the coding and functionalities details. While undertaking this type of test, various classes and their related coding are inspected and reviewed to ensure that they are consistent with the requirements of the project and that they conform with best practices (Braude & Bernstein, 2010).

On the contrary is black box testing undertaken by both technical and non-technical project team members. In this type of testing, a high level of abstraction is embraced during the testing operation where testers just check on whether the software is working as expected with no interest on how it is designed to achieve the functionalities under evaluation (Braude & Bernstein, 2010).

There are a number of ways in which white box and black box testing approaches are implemented that depend on the stage of development. The most basic test is unit testing which is quite favourable for modern development approaches such as Agile and DevOps methodologies (Mueller & Wickett, 2016). Unit testing involves testing each part of the system during development before the part is integrated into the system.

After the units are tested and integrated into the system, integration system follows to check the compatibility between various system units (Pressman, 2010). This approach tests

whether the different units combined together to form the whole systems, function as expected. Additionally, regression testing is undertaken as a complementary test to assess if system integration creates any malfunction or introduces any bugs in the system (Blaude & Bernstein).

Acceptance testing holistically tests the final product and no one at this point may be interested in the process that led to the product or how the project was managed. What matters is whether the product is doing what it is expected to do. It is however worth noting that, it doesn't mean that because the developers followed user requirements to the latter, the product will be accepted. In essence, this is the test that most development methodologies aim to satisfy; that is, the final product should not only meet user requirements, but should also address their current business needs (Allardice, 2013). Working together with the customer throughout the project is therefore a necessity.

Figure 3.0: Different types of software testing

Source: (Pressman, 2010)

2.3.4.2 Embracing Agile: Test Driven Development (TDD)

As is the case with software development methodologies, software testing can also follow a pre-determined lifecycle. TDD is one of such lifecycles. This cycle is not a replacement of SDLC but a complementation to it; more specifically to the testing phase. TDD therefore is a practice that requires a developer to follow a simple strategy where a test is written before the program code and then the actual code that solves the problem is verified against the code (Allardice, 2013).

TDD is an automated process and it is not an approach that replaces all other types of testing discussed earlier but a way of comprehensively dealing with unit testing which in most of the cases is the most vulnerable and difficult to fix late in complex projects (Pressman, 2010). As Allardice (2013) states, this test will not fix everything and so is agile, design patterns, OOD or any other approach. The objective is to produce very high quality code as a milestone towards the development of software that meets and exceeds customer’s expectations.

While developing android applications using java programming language, JUnit has been proven to be the most preferred testing framework (Allardice, 2013), although Nolan, Cinar, & Truxall (2014) propose Robolectric as alternative to JUnit. This testing approach is similar across programming languages with each language having its own xUnit framework; that is, NUnit, PyUnit, CppUnit and OCUit for .Net, Python, C++ and Objective-C programming languages respectively (Allardice, 2013).

TDD is based on assertions or facts and anything that violates a predefined assertion will not pass the test. It has three steps popularly known as red, green and refactor illustrated below.

Figure 3.1: Iterative Test Driven Development Lifecycle

Source: Android (2018)

While referencing the figure above, the red means that we start by writing a test that will fail and watch it fail, green means we add logic (code) so that the test succeeds, and after that, we refactor to test if there are any errors in the code. If the refactor step keeps on succeeding as the development process progresses, the unit, regression and integration testing will have succeeded leading to clean code (Allardice, 2013).

One of the main challenges in software development is coming up with a solution that makes a complex application user-friendly, easy to maintain and at the same time meet the user requirements (Pressman, 2010). This challenge as well as many others are brought about by the inherent complexity of software project (Braude & Bernstein, 2010). The fact that different software developers can use different processes, approaches and methods to achieve the same goal, makes this process a complex one (Pressman, 2010). Testing then becomes the only way a developer can find out whether they are on the right track and whether the system meets the intended objective.

2.4 Gaps in literature

There is extensive literature on the areas of focus with literature on software engineering, software development methodologies and software security at overwhelming levels. This literature is extremely useful and very well communicated to aid this project. But there are some major gaps identified during the review that this project aims to address.

First and foremost, most of the literature available is theoretical and its application is only on a limited scope. Where it has been applied, it is mostly applied in the development of web based applications. While the approaches in developing mobile applications and other software may be the same, the challenges presented by the different environments vary a lot. Additionally, it would be prudent to test if the theories and frameworks reviewed would still help in meeting customer requirements in a modern environment. Furthermore, some new developments in technology and methodologies have not been well tested in research environments with DevOps methodology being a good example.

While the scope of this project does not allow addressing all the aforementioned gaps, it is expected that other researchers will address them in the future. However, this project is designed to address some of major gaps identified in the literature review process. This is achieved through the application and evaluation of as many as possible software engineering theories, paradigms and best practices in a mobile development environment. An additional milestone in this project involves evaluating whether the software development methodologies can work in practice. Although the scope of the project limits a holistic application of most methodologies especially those developed with project team dynamics in mind, there are still a number of applicable practices inclined towards the project aim and objectives that the project aims to address.

2.5 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, software engineering approaches have been classified into three categories; namely, software development methodologies, software engineering paradigms and best practices in software development. The methodologies are further classified as either traditional or modern - with agile and its processes such as Scrum, Kanban, DevOps and FDD classified in the modern category and the waterfall, incremental process, evolutionary process, spiral and concurrent models grouped as traditional. The second classification is the software development paradigms such as object oriented analysis and design approaches and design patterns. Review these approaches, has helped in achieving the first objective of the project.

The second objective of the project required a technical review of the development and testing methodologies applied when developing secure android applications. To achieve it, the objective is dissected into four researchable units. The first unit involves a review of the methodologies employed by other researchers while developing similar applications, the second one investigates security requirements in mobile applications and proposes how it should be implemented, while the last one reviews software testing methodologies with a focus on testing strategies and test driven development methodology. Chapter three follows next with the detailed methodology employed in the project.

CHAPTER THREE

PROJECT METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The chapter gives the detailed methodology employed in the project. It outlines the steps on how the project aim and objectives were achieved with explanations as to why the approaches used were the best for this project. Whereas the aim of the project was to address the security issues associated with online payments and consequently promote customer's trust in buying online, the objectives formulated to achieve this aim revolved around the development, testing and evaluation of an android application that addresses the problem. The key milestones in achieving these objectives were the processes and methods discussed in this chapter.

The chapter starts by explaining the importance of various methods and processes in a research study and on how they can help in achieving the project aims and objectives. Furthermore, important facets of the research process such as the research philosophy, research strategy, research methods, data analysis and ethical considerations are explained and discussed in this chapter.

3.2 Research Philosophy

The way a researcher undertakes a research in any given field is determined by the research philosophy employed in each project. Biggam (2008) explains research philosophy as the belief about how data for solving a phenomenon should be collected, presented and analysed.

Since the objective of a scientific study is to test the facts about a certain belief or theory (Biggam, 2008). The results of the project are expected to be highly influenced by the unpredictable behaviour of human beings. To counter this, this project was undertaken with the belief that, reality can be interpreted in various ways depending on when, why and the context of the interpretations (Biggam, 2008). Additionally, this project was also used to test our belief that; by gathering user requirements and designing a system that reflects on them while following the best practices, their problems would be addressed. In this project; the belief was that customer trust on using ecommerce platforms can be addressed by providing them with a mobile payment as an alternative.

It is difficult to quantify this and therefore an interpretivism research philosophy guides on what kind of data should be collected and on how it should be collected and analysed to understand what kind of a system is needed to solve the problem at hand (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009). Additionally, this project relies on scientific evidence through the application of theory in software development. Due to this, two philosophical views are employed in different parts of the project. First, the interpretivism view is used while gathering user requirements and second, positivism view is used while testing software engineering theories.

3.3 Research Strategy

The research strategy employed in this project is better explained if we start with the problem; that is; customers tend to shy away from buying online because they do not trust the currently available online payments methods. The project aim is therefore to provide an alternative mechanism that customers will not shy away from.

Above withstanding, a practical action research was employed to solve this problem. This was undertaken while following the following plan of actions.

- i. Defining the problem and clarification of the project aim and objectives.
- ii. Review of literature relating to software engineering approaches and on the development and testing of secure android applications for mobile payments.
- iii. Application of research to solve the problem. This entailed the practical application of theory and paradigms in the development of an android application.
- iv. Project evaluation: at this point, the level of achievement of the aims and objectives of the study was assessed and the conclusions that help the readers of the report evaluate its relevance and applicability were also highlighted. Additionally, based on the inherent limitations, challenges and scope of the project, some key recommendations for areas for further of research are made.

With the four steps above in mind, the research is divided into two categories based on how the action steps were undertaken and the kind of data used in the project.

3.4 Data collection

The project followed a triangulation technique that involved collection of both primary and secondary data from various sources (Biggam, 2008) as explained below.

3.4.1 Primary Data

Primary data is data collected from a source in its raw form; it is data that is collected for the first time (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009). Two types of primary data was collected for the project: 1) project primary data collected during the software development and testing processes and 2) primary data collected from the customer and the users (people) using semi-structured interviews.

3.4.1.1 Semi-structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were administered to a random sample of five Kenyan business people to aid in identifying the systems requirements. Random sampling was used to enhance the credibility and validity of the research process (Biggam, 2008). Additional measures employed to enhance credibility include; obtaining data from only credible sources and proper referencing of supporting evidence.

3.4.1.1 Primary data from the mobile Application

This data was obtained from the project during development to illustrate how the project met the related aim and objectives, and to validate the application of theories during the development process. This data includes screenshots and codes to illustrate the application of an agile methodology, design patterns and object oriented analysis, design and programming.

3.4.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data was obtained from both electronic and non-electronic sources. Sources of secondary data used in the project included; published journal articles, articles in periodicals, articles from newspapers and magazines, online and offline books, research publications, software documentations, conference proceedings, websites, media reports, government reports among others. Majority of the secondary data collected for the project was used to guide the software development and in literature review.

3.5 Framework for data analysis

The analysis strategy used depended on the intended use of the results and is better explained in line with the research objectives. This framework is classified into two categories; that is, 1) literature analysis: for the objectives that required literature review and 2) project analysis for the objectives that required software development and testing.

3.5.1 Literature Analysis

The first and the second objectives were achieved through a critical literature review. The main aim of this was to gather skills, knowledge and tactics needed in tackling the project and to understand how other scholars tackled similar projects in the past.

The analysis involved breaking the field of interest into sub topics related to the project objectives. These sub-topics were then examined in detail to find their characteristics and features and where possible broken further for deeper analysis. The features and explanations given by different secondary data sources were compared, contrasted and critiqued to help in forming our own opinions and conclusions. Additional analysis involved, evaluating the merits and demerits of employing the theories, strategies and practices congruent with the project objectives.

3.5.2 Project Analysis

The third objectives required the application of theories, practices and principles in problem resolution. This required application of well-engineered software development approaches in problem solving; in this case, in the development and testing of a secure android application for mobile payments. To achieve this objective, the project was analysed using object-oriented analysis, design and programming employed throughout the application development process. This required an additional breakdown of project analysis into three categories; namely, systems analysis and design, analysis of the application development and finally application testing and evaluation.

3.5.2.1 System Analysis and Design

The systems analysis and design approach employed in this project comprised of four steps advocated for in the object-oriented software engineering approach (Allardice, 2013); these are, description of the application, identification of the main objects, description of system interactions and finally, coming up with the class diagram. Unified Modelling language (UML) was used for drawing diagrams needed for this analysis. The diagrams used to describe the application include; use case diagrams, user stories, sequence diagrams, flow charts and class diagrams among others. The databases used by the application were also identified as part of main objects and their interactions with the system analysed and designed.

The analysis at this stage mostly relied on primary data from semi-structured interviews and some secondary data from the literature review. This data was used to identify user requirements that formed the basis of the use case diagram that defined the application classes and methods.

3.5.2.2 Analysis of the application development

This analysis involved breaking down the project into processes that makes up the final product to meet the project objectives. Analysis at this stage followed Blaude & Bernstein (2010), 4 Ps of the software development; that is, people, process, project and the product.

People analysis involved identifying the stakeholders involved in the project, their roles and how their contributed to the failure or success of the project. The aim of this analysis was to identify the dynamics of project management for future improvements. The scope of the project did not allow a holistic analysis of the project stakeholders and therefore the application development methodology borrowed from different agile practices applicable to the project.

Additional project analysis involved critiquing the methodologies employed in the project whether formal or informal, with an aim of finding which would work best in a similar project environment.

Furthermore the process involved listing and critiquing the steps, procedures, methods, techniques among other practices employed during the development of the mobile application. This involved breaking down various features in Android application development process to finer details and giving reasons as to why particular aspects, features or techniques were preferred over others. The programming language, frameworks, databases and the development environments used to achieve project objectives were also broken down, contrasted and the merits and demerits of their application in this project highlighted.

The application of software engineering approaches was also analysed and illustrated with diagrams, code excerpts and screenshots of the application that show how various aspects of OOD; such as, composition, abstraction, inheritance and encapsulation were employed in the project and the reasons for their preference. Furthermore, best practices such as the use of design patterns were also illustrated.

3.5.2.3 Analysis of the Application Testing and Evaluation

This comprised of the product analysis and entailed evaluating the application in terms of whether it met the intended objectives in terms of features, characteristics, functionality, and user acceptance. User testing and evaluation also formed part of this analysis. The analysis involved evaluating the types of testing that were deemed appropriate to test the application and giving examples of how they were used to test the application with supporting evidence.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Central to research are ethical issues that need to be upheld throughout the research process. These issues are inherent in all research projects and their consideration is paramount. With this understanding, the researcher was expected to differentiate the rights and wrongs in this research study.

This research process was undertaken in a clear and straightforward way to ensure that ethics were upheld throughout. In particular, the issues discussed below were conscientiously attended to during the project.

Prior to research, all information on what was expected from the participants was communicated in advance. This entailed informing the participants about interviewer intended use of the data to be collected and guaranteeing them that: their responses will be anonymous, participation voluntary, and that they may withdraw anytime from the process if they wish, and skip any questions they were uncomfortable to answer.

During the research, the interviews were conducted in a polite way with no misleading questions asked. Furthermore, the research was also designed to avoid any physical and psychological harm and no contentious or sensitive questions were asked. The research also did not involve any observation exercise. Over and above that, no animals, people with disability, children, patients, people in custody, vulnerable groups or illegal groups were engaged in the research. However, due to the random sampling of the participants, measures such as anonymity of the participants were put in place just in case any such groups participated in the research without the researcher's knowledge.

Lastly, this project was not funded by any external parties, the data collected was used for this project only and no disclosures to any third parties are needed. The anonymity of the participants is therefore upheld and the participants were asked to get in touch if they may be interested in the final results of the project.

3.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter encompasses the methodology employed in the research study. It outlines the philosophical position that inspired the research to be undertaken as described despite there being a variety of ways in which the objective of the project would have been met. Additionally, a discussion on the research strategy and the steps undertaken to achieve the four objectives of the project are highlighted. This includes a discussion of the action steps in practical research, which included data collection and analysis, project design, analysis and implementation, and finally testing and evaluation. The type of data used to achieve this and how it was collected and analysed and used in the project is also described. The project ends with the ethical issues considered upheld during the research, and a discussion of how they were addressed prior, during and after the project. Chapter four follows next with presentation of the artefact, its analysis and testing.

CHAPTER FOUR

DEVELOPING A SECURE ANDROID APPLICATION FOR MOBILE PAYMENTS

4.1 Introduction

This section of the report addresses the third objectives of the project that required the development and testing of a secure android application for mobile payments. To achieve this objective, the project was broken down into four iterative phases. Each phase is presented together with its execution strategy and samples of supporting evidences of its processes using one or several illustrations that explain the application of: Agile methodology, OODP and design patterns in each of the phases.

4.2 Embracing agile project management methodology in mobile Application development

The system was sub-divided into four sub-systems. These sub-systems comprised iterative development cycles that involved system analysis and design, programming and testing for both functional and non-functional requirements as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 4.0: Agile/Iterative cycle in programming phases

Figure 4.0: Programming phases in the project with iterative system analysis and design, programming and testing of each phase.

The development processes in the sub-systems shown in Figure 4.0 above were reviewed iteratively in the development period in line with the practices of the agile methodology. This

approach offered flexibility in design, programming and testing of the application throughout the development period.

4.3 Object Oriented System analysis and Design

System analysis and design was the first iterative phase of the project. The phase started with a critical investigation of the problems solved by the application. The solutions that solve the problems are presented using various UML diagrams. The phase involved undertaking the following activities:

4.3.1 GATHERING OF USER REQUIREMENTS

This process started with data collection using semi-structured interviews administered to five interviewees, who comprised of small scale traders based in Nairobi Kenya. The selection of the traders was random to avoid bias. The objective of this exercise was to clarify user requirements and to gather additional requirements that would guide the application development process. This process also facilitated communication and collaboration with customers in line with the requirements of the agile project management methodology embraced throughout the project.

Before the main interviews were administered, a pilot interview was administered on a friend to test the effectiveness of the interview. A sample of the final interview is provided with this report as annexe one.

Table 4.0: Presentation of the Interview results

User requirements	System requirements	User Stories
Simplified way to add products for sale	User Interface, database, and logic to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add products • Edit products • Delete products • List Products 	Sellers should easily: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add, Edit, and delete products. • Products should have photos, prices and descriptions.
Management of products on sale.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A secure user management system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only sellers can sell, edit and delete their products. • Buyers can view products on sale.
Security of products and payments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access control system • Payment validation system • Order processing system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The system should restrict unauthorised access of products. • The system should automatically allow users to download products after successful payment. • The systems should have a secure mobile payment system

Table 4.0: Summary of the results of the interview showing the common themes that formed the user requirements used in describing the mobile application.

As shown in the summary table above, interviews with sellers showed that, there is a consistent need for a good system design that is scalable, affordable and easy to maintain. Therefore, to allow flexibility as requested by the interviewed traders - who sold diverse types of products at the time of the interview, the system was designed with three types of users in mind; that is, anonymous users, product sellers and product buyers.

4.3.2 Describing the application using use case diagrams

Use case diagrams are the basic diagrams used to explain the interactions between the user and the system (Faitelson & Tyszberowicz, 2017). They are used in this project as the starting point of the system analysis and design process.

Since the project employed an iterative approach, the designs in the following sections are the final designs after several revisions during the project lifecycle as necessitated by changes in design and functional specifications during the development and testing period.

Figure 4.1: Use case diagram of the system

Figure 4.1: A customer first makes a decision to buy a certain product; in this case an EBook. They therefore require a list of all products available, their detailed descriptions, images and any other details relevant for their evaluation.

One of the "Manage Cart" operations in the shopping cart is payment. Users must register with the system first before paying for shopping cart items and only registered users who have paid for products can save an order to the shared online database. The shopping cart list is saved in user's local database until they delete all the items from the list or have fully paid

for the items in the cart. If users have added items for sale, they can as well edit or delete any products associated with them.

Figure 4.2: Use case diagram for the shopping cart unit

Figure 4.2: Addresses the customers need for the system that allows them to add, edit, view, and remove products from the shopping cart – and to finally pay for them.

4.3.3. The main objects of the application

The use case diagrams presented in section 4.2 above helped in the identification of the main objects that make up the application. The conceptual model presented in figure 4.4 below is used to show those objects as well as the associations and interactions between them.

Figure 4.3: The Conceptual model of the application

Figure 4.4 above presents the sequence diagram of a section of the application that handles payment process.

4.3.4 Visualizing the application with class diagram

A class diagram visually represents the application to clearly bring out the concepts behind object oriented design (Faitelson & Tyszberowicz, 2017). This diagram helped in identification of various objects that were later encapsulated as activities, services or interfaces for the application.

Figure 4.4: The class diagram of the application with the main classes

Figure 4.4: The class diagram with main objects of the application represented using a class diagrams. The arrows show where an object inherits its properties from (Inheritance in OOP).

4.3.5 Database design and development

After system analysis and design, three types of databases were evaluated for use by the application. These are: Cloud NoSQL (Not only Sequence Query Language) database, SQLite relational database, and MYSQL relational database.

4.3.5.1 Cloud NoSQL Database

Firebase NoSQL database was evaluated and preferred as the main database for the application. Firebase database is genre of NoSQL database classified in the category of document databases (Gupta, Tyagi, & Panwar, 2018). The database uses a key and value pair

with the key acting as the index and the pair as the data store. Data is stored as an infinite array of JSON object that is referenced using unique key index (Firebase, 2018).

Firestore database is seamlessly connected to a data store to allow for internal storage of files, images and other documents, a feature not available in relational databases (Firebase, 2018).

Table 4.1: Firebase Cloud Database: Features Used in the application		
Firestore feature	Uses	Objects
Authentication	User Registration, User Management, Session Management, Access Security	User registration, User Login, Password Change, Email Verification, Profile Update, Account deletion
Database	Storage of data such as Text, Numbers, Urls, Messages (Structured and Semi-structured data)	Objects for Adding, Editing/Updating and Deletion of data stored. Data stored in form of JSON file in variables (Long, Double, String and Integers or as collections, arrays, among other formats).
Storage	Storage and update of Files, Images, documents, and digital products on sale etc.	Add Edit, Update and Delete files and documents referenced by an URL that is saved as a string in the database.

Table 4.1: Three of the Firestore features used by the application, Firestore offer several other additional functionalities beyond the scope of this project.

4.3.5.2 Relational Databases: SQLite and MySQL Databases

Although Firestore database provided high flexibility, scalability and ease of use, the following limitations of the database led to the use of SQLite and MySQL as additional databases for the application:

- a. There was no need to share personal shopping data over the internet. SQLite database was used to store personalised shopping data in the user's device without sharing it over the web.
- b. Although Firestore database can adequately meet the need for direct storage of third party payment responses. The database supports limited programming languages; that is, Python, NodeJs, Golang and Java (Firestore, 2018). Additionally, implementing the languages listed above require additional resources such as specialised servers and new skills beyond the scope of this project.

The implementation strategies of these databases are discussed in later sections of the report.

4.3.5.3 NoSQL Databases vs. Relational databases

The choice of NoSQL database as the main database for the application was motivated by what the users expect the system to do for them and the type of media the application relies on. Firebase NoSQL database was found optimal for this application because of the following merits:

- i. The database relies on a highly de-normalised structure that is very flexible during application development. For instance; it was easy to implement database structures during development using very simple coding and without the need for prior designs of entity relationship diagrams and database structures needed while using relational databases.
- ii. Furthermore, instead of the table structure employed in relational databases, Firebase NoSQL database uses flexible JSON arrays objects. In cases where relationships are needed, the key of the related array group is stored as an extra value in the array object for reference; typically, the same way relational databases use foreign keys.

The major drawback encountered with NoSQL database was data redundancy and limited resources for developers. These factors were sacrificed in this project for the efficiency and flexibility needed in the project.

4.3.6 Application Development: The User Management Unit

This was the first unit developed for the application; its development involved adopting the authentication system inbuilt in Firebase for the application. This involved programming for functionalities such as: user registration, management of user data, user validation using email, password management, among other requirements of a user management system.

User authentication helps in managing security by allowing or denying users access to various functionalities of the system depending on user type. Furthermore, the system also serves as the security control point for users who want to check out for payment.

Figure 4.5 User registration system: Control of navigation between activities

Figure 4.5: Illustrates two use cases of the authentication system in addition to its very basic uses such as verifying user actions such as; adding, editing and updating data related to them. It shows how the authentication system controls navigation between activities where each activity is an object that encapsulate several methods.

The system checks if user is logged on to Firebase database as shown in code below.

```

FirebaseUser user = FirebaseAuth.getInstance().getCurrentUser();
if (user != null) {
    // User is signed in
} else {
    // No user is signed in
}

```

The following code below was used during development to get details of a registered user when needed for various functionalities and controls in an object.

```

FirebaseUser user = FirebaseAuth.getInstance().getCurrentUser();
if (user != null) {
    // Name, email address, and profile photo Url
    String name = user.getDisplayName();
    String email = user.getEmail();
    Uri photoUrl = user.getPhotoUrl();
    // Check if user's email is verified
    boolean emailVerified = user.isEmailVerified();
    // Getting Firebase Userid
    String uid = user.getUid();
}

```

The code below explains how the user is logged on anonymously and how to check if the log in process was successful or not. The Log cat messages were used during for testing to check the condition that was executed.

```

 mAuth.signInAnonymously()
    .addOnCompleteListener(this, new OnCompleteListener<AuthResult>() {
        @Override
        public void onComplete(@NonNull Task<AuthResult> task) {
            if (task.isSuccessful()) {
                // Sign in success, update UI with the signed-in user's information
                Log.d(TAG, "signInAnonymously:success");
                FirebaseUser user = mAuth.getCurrentUser();
                updateUI(user);
            } else {
                // If sign in fails, display a message to the user.
                Log.w(TAG, "signInAnonymously:failure", task.getException());
                Toast.makeText(AnonymousAuthActivity.this, "Authentication failed.",
                    Toast.LENGTH_SHORT).show();
                updateUI(null);
            }

            // ...
        }
    });

```

4.3.7 The mobile commerce unit

The mobile commerce sub-system forms the main application and is interconnected with the user management system, the database system and the payment system. This sub-system has four main objects that encapsulate different methods to support its functionalities.

Table 4.2: Activities that make up the mobile commerce unit

Units	Functionalities
Product Listing Activity	This object (activity) was designed to support the user by displaying a list of the items available for sale. Access to the activity is connected to majority of the activities in the application due to its importance in the application.
Product Detail Activity	This activity gives a detailed view of the product selected by the user from the list. It also forms the starting point for adding and updating an item in the shopping cart as well as editing and deleting it from the database.
Product Storage Activity	The product storage activity is the starting point of selling digital products. This activity implements methods to allow registered sellers to upload a Pdf

	file (an EBook for sale) to the firebase storage. After a successful upload, a link that is only accessible to users who have successfully paid for the uploaded product is made available in the orders database for product download.
Add/Edit Product Activity	This activity allows adding and updating of products related to a user account. Edit functionality is started from the detail activity when user click on the edit icon where a method is implemented to validate ownership of the product so that users can only edit products they own.
Shopping Cart Activity	This is the starting point of the payment process. In addition to facilitating shopping cart operations such as adding and removal of items from the cart, this activity has a check out button which allows users to start the payment process.

4.3.8 Developing a secure mobile payment unit

The payment unit is accessed only when the user checks out as a registered user. In cases where the checking out user is logged on anonymously, their anonymous account is deleted, and the user is directed to the registration activity where they can either create a new account or navigate further to log in or recover lost password. The payment system is a complex system that was developed while embracing a high level of abstraction using a façade design pattern.

4.3.8.1 Façade design Pattern: Encapsulation, Abstraction and Composition

Façade design pattern is a structural design pattern that provides a unified interface to a set of objects (Gamma *et al.*, 1997). The pattern also provides well defined higher-level interface that eases the use of sub-systems (Gamma *et al.*, 1997). This pattern was suited for this project because of the aforementioned reasons. Additionally, by embracing this pattern, it was easier to develop the payment system in phases where each object was developed and tested before it was integrated with the object it supports. This made it easy to develop and test the system for security and functionality iteratively.

Despite this sub-system being complex, the façade design pattern employed simplifies it through a façade (MpesaMainActivity.java) that supports abstraction and composition as shown in the figure 4.6 below.

Figure 4.6: Façade Design pattern illustration and its application in the project

Figure 4.6: Shows implementation of façade design pattern on the left side and its illustration on the right side. MPesa Main Activity is the façade activity in this application. Composition is shown by relationships of the objects encapsulated by the façade design while abstraction is used to hide the complexity from the system users.

As a result of this implementation, the user is able to complete the payment process in the three simple steps represented in the flow chart below by parallelograms.

Figure 4.7: A flowchart diagram of the payment process

Figure 4.7: A successful payment process has three steps and but very many processes hidden from the user through abstraction.

The three steps that require user input are represented with parallelograms. These are: entering payer’s mobile number, entering secret pin on the Mpesa interface presented to the user if correct mobile number is entered, and finally verifying the payment using the receipt obtained in form of a text message.

4.3.8.2 Demystifying the payment process: Chain of responsibility design pattern

By using abstraction, three autonomous systems are interconnected to complete the payment process seamlessly. Below is a sequence diagram of the payment process.

Figure 4.8: Sequence diagram of a successful payment process

The first step in the payment process involves interacting with an external system; the Safaricom’s Mpesa API. To achieve the intended results from the API, actions such as formatting mobile number and time stamp, generating a valid authorisation token and creating and sharing of public key for the encryption of the transaction, must be completed in a chain of events. Chain of responsibility design pattern was used to interlink these events seamlessly. According to Gamma *et al.* (1997), a chain of responsibility design pattern:

“Avoids coupling the sender of a request to its receiver by giving more than one object a chance to handle the request and passing it along the chain until the final object handles it”

In the payment process, the chain starts when the user enters a mobile number and clicks on the submit button. The objects encapsulated in the façade activity (MpesaMainActivity.java) are used to handle various requests in a chain until success or error message is received. Assuming a correct mobile number had been entered, the chain is halted by an automatic request for secret pin number and continues when user authorises the transaction with their correct pin.

While using this pattern, objects that send the request have no explicit knowledge of the object that will handle it (Gamma *et al.*, 1997), in fact, unlike in previous activities where moving to the next activity was initiated with intents, in this case, the returned object; Safaricom's Mpesa payment Toolkit, is external to the system. An improvisation was required to connect the external system with the application to verify the payment.

4.3.8.3 Receiving and saving the payment feedback to MySQL database

A key challenge faced while developing the payment system was defining how feedback data from the external system was to be collected and passed to the android application. In their documentation, Safaricom (2018) requires an http listener/server that can receive JSON data where they can send feedback of the payment. A call back URL that points to the server must be registered with them to receive such a feedback. Below is a sample JSON data received by the http server after a successful payment.

Sample JSON data received by the http server after a successful payment

```
{
  "Body": {
    "stkCallback": {
      "MerchantRequestID": "26452-605723-2",
      "CheckoutRequestID": "ws_CO_23042018105859659",
      "ResultCode": 0,
      "ResultDesc": "The service request is processed successfully.",
      "CallbackMetadata": {
        "Item": [
          {
            "Name": "Amount",
            "Value": 1
          },
          {
            "Name": "MpesaReceiptNumber",
            "Value": "MDN6ZJE4XG"
          },
          {
            "Name": "Balance"
          },
          {
            "Name": "TransactionDate",
            "Value": 20180423105912
          },
          {
            "Name": "PhoneNumber",
            "Value": 254722200121
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  }
}
```

The Http server was designed to analyse the data received to save its important parts in a MySQL database. The android application accesses that data from MYSQL database using a WebView that renders https URL to display a textbox where the user is expected to enter the transaction receipt number. Entering the correct reference number completes the transaction and the user is redirected to orders listing activity that has URL to download the products they have paid for.

Mining data from the JSON object presented in the previous section involves getting values for: amount, MpesaReceiptNumber, Balance, Transaction date and phone number and saving them in the MySQL database table called transaction.

4.3.8.4 Payment verification: MySQL to Android using a JavaScript Interface

The final phase of the payment process was complex and daunting to implement because of challenges brought about by improved security in android API 23 and above and very technical requirements for transferring data between web and mobile using Secure Socket Layer (SSL) and Transport Layer Security (TLS) encryption.

With the aforementioned challenges withstanding, the following three approaches to securely transfer the payment data saved in MYSQL database to the mobile application were evaluated for use. Only one of these approaches passed the test of time while the other two are recommended for further research.

4.3.8.4.1 Firebase database as bridge between http server and the android application

This approach requires the payment feedback data to be saved in firebase database directly. It is a very simple strategy but its major limitation was inability of firebase to support PHP programming language directly (Firebase, 2018). A server upgrade is necessary to allow this functionality. Since a shared server in which access to Secure Shell (SSH) cryptographic network protocol was restricted, was used for the project, it was not possible to perform additional server configurations for this project. These limitations hindered the implementation of firebase as a bridge for android, which is the easiest implementation. Future improvement of the application should involve using https servers that support either python or NodeJs to receive payment feedback and allows direct saving of data to Firebase database.

4.3.8.4.2 JSON data over Secure Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTPs)

This is another popular approach for Android web communication because of its independence on the database used with the android application. Applications that use MySQL as their main database are expected to use this approach. However, this approach is not straight forward while using encrypted data (https) because it requires custom programming for secure data exchange process. This programming was time consuming and the available time was not enough to complete and test the approach.

4.3.8.4.3 Accessing JavaScript data from the web to android with via a JavaScript Interface

WebView is an element in android layout that displays web pages from a given URL. Just like a text view is used to display text, WebView is used to display web content. By default, the option to display html (static content) is enabled while JavaScript is disabled. In this project, JavaScript was enabled at run time and a JavaScript interface created in the android verify payment activity to receive JavaScript data from a JavaScript function inside a PHP file in the http web server. To access data, users must click on a pre-designed HTML button on the rendered on the WebView from the web server. Clicking on it triggers the chain of events.

4.5.8.5 Chain of responsibility design pattern in payment verification

The following steps are the final payment steps, which is a chain of events implemented with a chain of responsibility design pattern and encapsulated with a façade design pattern.

- i. HTML page hosted on same PHP server that hosts the MySQL database is rendered on Android WebView. When user clicks the submit button, the text input is sent to a PHP form processor hosted in the same server directory using POST method.

- ii. The PHP form processor receives the reference and executes a query to check if the reference exists in the transaction table. If it exists, details of amount, phone, receipt and date are obtained and saved as PHP variables.

```
$ref = $_POST["reference"];
```

```

$stmt = mysqli_stmt_init($conn);
if (mysqli_stmt_prepare($stmt, "SELECT transaction_amount, transaction_receipt, transaction_balance,
                                transaction_date, transaction_mobile
                                FROM transaction
                                WHERE transaction_receipt=? AND transaction_status=?"))
{
    mysqli_stmt_bind_param($stmt, "ss", $ref, $status);
    mysqli_stmt_execute($stmt);
    mysqli_stmt_bind_result($stmt, $amount, $receipt, $balance, $date, $phone);
    mysqli_stmt_fetch($stmt);
    mysqli_stmt_close($stmt);
}

```

- iii. The variables are put in a standardised format and encrypted using SHA512 open SSL digest to create 128-digit hexadecimal number that is saved as a PHP variable. The number produced by Open SSL digest is of the same length irrespective of the size of message that was encrypted.

```

$pass = ":".$amount.":".$phone.":".$receipt.":".$date.":";
$pass = openssl_digest($pass, 'sha512');

```

- iv. Amount, reference and encrypted string are converted to a JavaScript variable. The amount value is pre-pended and reference number appended to the encrypted String inside a JavaScript getValues () function that is triggered by clicking the HTML button on the form processor.

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<body>
<form name='ref' method='post' action='index.php'>
  <button type="button" value="" id="btnOK" onclick="getValues();ok.performClick(this.value);">OK</button>
</form>
<script>
document.getElementById("btnOK").click();
document.getElementById("btnOK").style.visibility = "hidden";
function getValues() {
  var amount = "<?php echo $amount; ?>";
  var receipt = "<?php echo $receipt; ?>";
  if (receipt == "") {
    var pass = "NULL";
    document.getElementById("btnOK").value = pass;
  }else{
    var pass = amount+"#"+<?php echo $pass; ?>+"$"+receipt;
    document.getElementById("btnOK").value = pass;
  }
}
</script>
</body>
</html>
<script>

```

From the code above, JavaScript click is automated so that the getValues () function is triggered without user intervention. The Android JavaScript interface receives data from the WebView by referencing the JavaScript functionality that processes the data and extracting the amount value from the string to check if the user has paid an amount equal or higher than the cart value for the transaction to be deemed complete.

```

private void displyContent(View view) {
    webView.clearView();
    webView.loadUrl(url);
    webView.reload();
    webView.addJavascriptInterface(performClick(strl) -> {
        String stringVariable = strl;
        if (strl.equalsIgnoreCase( anotherString: "NULL")) {
            webView.clearView();
            webView.reload();
            Toast.makeText( context: VerifyPayment.this, text: "Error: The receipt you entered is not valid!", Toast.LENGTH_SHORT).show();
        } else {
            //Check if amount paid is same as the cost
            String amt = strl.substring(0, strl.indexOf("#"));
            int amount = Integer.parseInt(amt);
            toPay = "1"; //REMOVE THIS AFTER TESTING
            int paid = Integer.parseInt(toPay);
            if (amount >= paid) {
                emptyCart();
                Toast.makeText( context: VerifyPayment.this, text: "Payment Received", Toast.LENGTH_SHORT).show();
                Intent intent = new Intent( packageContext: VerifyPayment.this, OrdersActivity.class);
                startActivity(intent);
                finish();
            } else if (amount < paid) {
                int bal = (paid - amount);
                Toast.makeText( context: VerifyPayment.this, text: "You paid less: Please to up Kshs: " + bal, Toast.LENGTH_SHORT).show();
                finish();
            }
        }
    }, name: "ok");
}
}

```

Once completed, the user is directed to the orders activity which displays all items ordered and paid by him with their download URLs for access.

4.6 Testing the android application

The testing process was administered to meet both functional and non-functional requirements of the project. Although a test-driven approach was preferable, the time available for the project did not allow for a carbon copy implementation of an automated TDD as described in Android (2018) documentation and by Allardice (2013). Instead, a simplified TDD version was used where the application activities/object, together with their supporting layouts, were created and tested at the very basic level of implementation. This approach involved testing the units iteratively as new features and functionalities were added to each sub-system and later to the system.

4.6.1 Functional Testing

Functional testing was used to evaluate if various units achieved their intended functionalities. This was done iteratively during the programming phase. The process involved using the following physical devices for testing.

- a. Samsung Grand 2, version 4.4.2, API 19 (KitKat)
- b. Nokia 5 API 26, version 8.0.0 (Oreo)

The test results given in the sections that follow reflect the testing results as observed from the two devices above. Functional testing involved either white box testing undertaken to test: the interface, code, logic and algorithms used in the programs, or black box testing, done to test if the units worked as expected after coding by evaluating the results of the program using some predetermined input test data.

4.6.1.1 White Box Testing

This was done to compare the code with the results for errors that may have occurred when implementing the application logic, algorithms, and conditions among others program features.

To simplify the process, log cat messages, Toast Messages, observations of the IDE behaviour and displays of expected output on a Text View were used as the main sources of white box test results. The following codes were used during testing.

Table 4.3: White Box Testing Strategies using

Test Strategy	Sample Test Implementation Strategy
Log cat messages	Log.d (“TAG”, “Message to display”);
Toast Message	Toast.makeText(this, “Message to display”, Toast.LENGTH_LONG).show();
TextView Display	Private TextView msgTxt; msgTxt = (TextView) findViewById (R.id.nameofTextUI); msgTxt.setText (“Message to display”);
Build/Clean	This involved running a build and/or clean functionality on android to detect programming errors present in the code. This process can be initiated from the menu or by running the application on an emulator or real device.

The first three strategies given in table 4.3 above helped in displaying a message that helps in evaluating if a certain line of code was executed as expected and to find out if a particular line of code was indeed executed and results obtained. This approach came in handy in unit testing to allow the most basic form of testing by making it easier to test the most basic units starting from: a line of code, a method, a class, an activity or the interactions between different system units.

Example of white box testing using log cat message

```
productUrl = (String) messageSnapshot.child("url").getValue();
input = productUrl.substring(productUrl.indexOf("%2F") + 3, productUrl.lastIndexOf( str: ".pdf"));
String product = "digital_Products/" + input + ".pdf";
Log.d( tag: "URL: ", msg: "Product URL Created");
```

In this code, product url is analysed to get the fields that identifies the product name as saved in Firebase storage. The default storage location for digital products is pre-appended, the file name appended and later the file extension (.pdf) appended as well. This approach was used to identify a product file to delete or update. Log cat message is used to check if the storage reference was well formatted in white box testing.

4.6.1.2 Black Box Testing

The objective of this test was to ensure that only correct inputs were entered into the system. This protects the system from malicious input and ensures that the system functions as intended. This requires testing of user inputs that are obtained through: direct data entry using the provided user interface elements such as Edit Text, click actions, recycler view, and buttons; or by selecting values from the spinner or options among other UI elements. Example is to display as toast message of the result of an operation before coming it to be saved in the database.

4.6.1.3 Integration Testing

This kind of testing is well explained using the user management system control of the mobile shopping unit. Since these two units were developed independent of each other and tested as different units, there was a need to test whether the two systems interacted as expected after they were integrated. Examples of the integrated tests done are given in the table below.

Table 4.4: Integrated Testing for Add, Edit and Delete a Product

Test Case	Unit Test Results	Integrated Test Results
Add new product	All users can add a new product for sale.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Registered users can add new products for sale. Anonymous users cannot add new products for sale.
Edit Product	All users can edit any product in the database.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Registered users can edit products associated with them Anonymous users cannot edit any products
Delete product	All users can delete any product from the database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Registered users can delete products associated with them Anonymous users cannot delete any products

The table above reflects that, users were not restricted from any action during unit testing; therefore, a user management system was developed to manage user access levels. This system was then integrated with the mobile commerce system. Integration testing was therefore used to evaluate the success of the integration process.

4.6.1.4 System Testing

System testing was done to test the whole system and involved testing for how each sub-system interacted with other sub-systems. Since unit and integrated testing were done during development, this phase involved testing if the sub-systems that make up the system interacted as expected with each other and with the underlying databases without affecting the functionalities of the units that supports them.

From the use case diagrams presented in section 4.2, the main reason why the user may use the system is either to sell or buy products. To achieve these goals, users are forced to undertake additional actions that improve the system usability and security. Usability actions may include: viewing of products list and details and adding, removing and updating items on the shopping cart. Security actions involve creation of user accounts, email verification and payment verification among others. This testing involved evaluating whether the flow of these events was well programmed to achieve all the requirements of the system.

Figure 4.9: System testing with anonymous user

Figure 4.9: Shows the process of evaluating whether a new user can complete a shopping experience using the system. Successful completion of the process meant that the system units were well integrated to meet one of the system functionalities of selling products to users.

Figure 5.0: Testing the system with a registered user

Figure 5.0: aimed at evaluating whether a registered user can add, edit and delete items. Completion of this process meant that the system was well developed for this functionality and can be used to add products to be listed for sale.

4.6.2 Non-functional testing: An overview

The application was tested for performance throughout the development period iteratively. Performance testing involved installing the application on a physical device to investigate activity loading time, screen displays and impact of various functionalities on battery life.

Test plan and results were project deliverable and are presented together with this report as an annex.

4.7 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, the artefact developed to meet the third objective of the project is presented, discussed, analysed. Furthermore, the functionality of the artefact is tested using approaches such as: black box, white box, unit, integrated and system testing. The illustrations that guided the application development process to meet the user needs as identified through a semi-structured interview are also presented and analysed. The section mainly dwells on the process of developing the application while the resulting artefacts comprising of the source codes and the executable Android Package File (APK), are presented together with this report as appendix one. The section is organised to further reflect the application of object-oriented programming by highlighting how OODP principles such as: abstraction, encapsulation, composition and inheritance were implemented in the project and supported with façade and chain of responsibility design patterns. The section also presents the databases, the user management system, the mobile commerce unit, the secure payment unit, and highlights the reasons why agile project management methodology was preferred over other methodologies. The challenges and limitations faced in the project are as well discussed throughout the chapter and remedial solutions proposed for future research, chapter five follows next with project evaluation, main conclusions and recommendations.

CHAPTER FIVE

PROJECT EVALUATION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Project evaluation

This chapter evaluates the whole project by highlighting the success or otherwise of the project in addressing the problem it was intended to address. It explains how each of the objectives formulated to achieve the project aim were addressed in the project.

5.1.1 Literature review on software engineering approaches

Chapter two, whose focus was on literature review, aimed at helping the researcher understand the subject matter under investigation in depth. During the review process, some gaps were identified and proposed for inclusion in the project for address, without diverting from the main project objectives. Identifying and addressing gaps identified in a literature review process helped in achieving the main purpose of a literature review in a research project.

One of the gaps identified during the review was limited application of software engineering theories and practices in a mobile application development environment. This project closed this gap by embracing a process that involved practical application of objected oriented concepts such as inheritance, abstraction, encapsulation and composition while developing a mobile application. The project has also practically demonstrated how design patterns can be used in software engineering; with façade and chain of responsibility design patterns as examples.

Another gap identified during literature review process was inadequate literature aiming to find out if theories could be applied in a project to meet customer requirements. This project has embraced a process that included gathering of customer requirements and using them to define the objects that make up the application to help in addressing customer needs thereby closing that gap.

5.1.2 Literature review on methodologies used in testing secure android applications.

Reviewing software testing methodologies brought useful insights on how software should be tested. For instance, by undertaking this review, the researcher understood the best approaches in software testing and was able to integrate them in the application development processes. The most recommended software testing approach is a test-driven development.

This approach was tested in the development period and modified to suit the project. Additionally, understanding the methodologies employed in software testing helped in speeding up the development leading to the completion of the project on time.

5.1.3 Development of a secure android application for mobile payments

This was the third objective of the project. It required application of software engineering theories and practices in the development of a secure android application for mobile payments. To achieve this objective in a seamless process, agile project management methodology was embraced for project management, and its use has been demonstrated throughout chapter four of the report.

The development process involved gathering user requirements, summarising them and using them as a guide for system analysis and design. The diagrams that support the application were designed using UML to describe the application. These diagrams are presented in chapter four to support the development process. The source code and the APK file of a reasonably secure android application for mobile payments that resulted from the process are presented together with this report.

5.1.4 Evaluating the effectiveness of the developed android application

The objective of this sub-section is to determine the merits or otherwise of the project in addressing the main challenge that motivated it; that is, securing online trade and its related payments with a mobile application. This objective is not quantifiable and therefore, the software security aspects identified during literature review, were used for security testing. Most of these security aspects were addressed in the project through the application of OOP and design patterns as follows:

- a) Abstraction was used to hide the most vulnerable parts of the application from the users. For instance, users cannot change the buy goods code that is used for receiving money because the interface that holds it is hidden from them.
- b) Encapsulation helped in putting the most secure methods of the application in one part and applying a higher level of security in that part. For example, the code for generating the payment authorisation token and the related security is generated at run time with the code for generating the tokens encapsulated within a secure activity abstracted from the users.

- c) Inheritance and composition prevents execution of standalone classes. If someone was able to access the source codes by decompiling the APK file. The classes that make up the application will not execute since some of their functionalities are extended to additional interfaces through composition while other are inherited from other classes through inheritance.

The security planning and implementation of the payment process is explained in detail in chapter four of the report. It involves using public key encryption to exchange payment details with the mobile service provider, hashing data using SHA512 standard and using HTTPs security for transferring data between the web and android application. Additionally, the security of the digital products uploaded by customers for sale is built in the project as follows:

- a) Using a document database with in-built security features. In this case, Firebase storage is integrated with the application to ensure security of customers digital products uploaded for sale.
- b) Integration of user management system with the application to control user actions on the application. This unit was developed to control users' access to various functionalities of the system. Customers can only edit, delete, or update their own products while anonymous users are disallowed from such actions.

5.2 Conclusions

As illustrated in the preceding evaluation, this project met its objectives within the available time. This achievement is highly attributed to agile project management methodology. It is therefore in-order to conclude that; agile project management methodology is a good methodology for managing complex software projects with strict deadlines; this is so because of the flexibility of the methodology. The methodology allows development of the most important parts of the software product and their iterative improvement and review at any time in the project.

Additionally, the project also shows that, methodology alone cannot lead to a successful project; therefore, the right development approaches must also be embraced. These approaches must be investigated through a thorough review of the available documentation and literature as illustrated by the project.

The project as well supports the application of theory in problem solving by embracing OODP, design patterns and a test-driven development in problem solving. In addition to this, the project has shown that, it is not the theories and concepts that are important but their application in problem solving. For instance, a TDD approach suited for the project was improvised.

Finally, is the importance of iterative testing in software development. This project has illustrated that, as projects grow in complexity, regression issues also increase. Therefore iterative testing should be embraced as an integral part of the software development. Although efforts have been made to make the product delivered for this project to be as secure as possible, the security of a system is as strong as its weakest point and the system still needs a lot of testing before it can be released to the market and even when it is ready for release, absolute security cannot be guaranteed in software projects.

5.3 Recommendations for future work

A lot of challenges and limitations have been highlighted throughout this project with the most notable one being time limitation. To investigate issues that could not be tackled due to those limitations, the following areas are recommended for research.

- a) An investigation on how programming languages such as python and NodeJs are used to save data directly to Firebase database for access by android applications. Such an investigation should also cover the technical requirements of the web platforms that run those languages.
- b) A critical investigation of the applicability or otherwise of DevOps methodology in a business environment while developing mobile applications. Such a project should investigate the impact of involving both technical and non-technical staffs in software projects on software quality and delivery time.
- c) An investigation on how the developed mobile commerce application can be improved to be offered online as a cloud application.
- d) An investigation into how the security and trust of supply chain processes managed by the application, can be improved using emerging technologies such as block chain for business.

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